

RIVER TERMINALS IN BRAZIL: A MULTIMODAL ANALYSIS OF THE STORAGE AND DISTRIBUTION OF PETROLEUM DERIVATIVES AND BIOFUELS

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Summary

The company River Terminals in Brazil operates by loading and unloading fuels that are derived from liquid petroleum and biofuels quickly, safely and efficiently, making it one of the most profitable companies in the Dislub Ecuador Group – GDE. The guiding question of this study is to know how the logistics of transporting fuel loading and unloading are carried out, the types of modes and the quantity of products entering and leaving the company River Terminals in Brazil. The methodology used is a case study. Secondary data collection is done through consultations on the company's websites, articles and electronic materials and for primary data, a technical visit and interview were carried out with the organization's main collaborators, in order to verify the loading and unloading process. of liquid products, the modes used in storage and distribution and the quantity of entry and exit of products between January and May 2022. This research is essential to understand the types of modes that the company uses according to the logistical characteristics of the region to the transport of liquid products and how it contributes to the supply of the states of Amazonas, Acre, Rondônia, Pará and Mato Grosso, through its agility during the operational process. In addition to being of great relevance to the area of Production Engineering, with an emphasis on Transport Logistics.

Keywords: Transport Modes; Storage; Distribution; Petroleum Derivative Products.

1. INTRODUCTION

Studying Logistics and *Supply Chain Management* during graduation, there was a need to apply the content taught in the classroom through everyday practice, as the content acquired is often applied in practice in order to arouse the interest of the student. university. After numerous topics covered, we arrived at the topic “Analysis of fuel storage and distribution of the company River Terminals in Brazil”. In the view of ANP (2021), the distribution of fuels is called secondary bases, these are locations that receive fuels derived from petroleum and biofuels directly from refineries following the standards determined by the National Agency for Petroleum, Natural Gas and Biofuels – ANP. According to Sant'Anna (2021), this type of distribution and storage is essential due to easy access, high speed and flexibility in the delivery and distribution of products, as well as generating employment and savings. These liquid products use maritime, road and/or pipeline modes, depending on the transport characteristics of the region.

Transport logistics encompasses the processes necessary to place products in the right place, at the right time, and under the desired conditions, while making the best possible contribution to the company in order to meet customer needs. And to overcome the supply needs in Amazonas and neighboring states, the Dislub Ecuador Group opened the company River Terminals in Brazil – RTB, being an enterprise for the storage and distribution of petroleum products, containing a total area of 107 thousand square meters, located in the municipality of Itacoatiara, 265 km from Manaus via the AM-010 highway. With a current capacity to store 104 million liters of fuel, the RTB represents a milestone in the region's economy. The ships that operated with only 40% of their cargo capacity and generated losses in logistics operations, resulting in an increase in the final price of the products transported, with the strategic installation of the company the scenario changed, as the vessels were able to travel with full load at any time of the year, regardless of the river flow, contributing to the supply of the states of Amazonas, Acre, Rondônia, Pará and Mato Grosso, and reducing the final price of the product.

Given the facts mentioned, this article aims to analyze the fuel storage and distribution process, identify the modes used and the quantity of products entering and leaving the company in a given period of the year.

2. METHODOLOGY

As for nature, it is basic research, due to the fact that it generates new and useful knowledge for the advancement of science without anticipated practical application. For Marques (2016), basic research is a systematic study, aimed at deepening knowledge of the fundamental aspects of phenomena and facts, as well as creating new questions in a process of incorporating and overcoming what has already been produced.

Regarding the objectives, it is an exploratory and descriptive research. It is exploratory because it seeks to understand the study variable as it presents itself, its meaning and the context in which it is inserted. (QUEIRÓZ, 1992). According to Babbie (1986), its main characteristic is the specificity of the questions, which is done from the beginning of the research, as the only way of approaching it. And it is descriptive research because it requires the researcher to provide a series of information about what they want to research. This type of study aims to describe the facts and phenomena of a given reality. (TRIVIÑOS, 1987). Still for the author, sometimes there is no critical examination of the information on the part of the investigator, and the results can be misleading; and data collection techniques, such as questionnaires, scales and interviews, can be subjective, only quantifiable, generating inaccuracy.

Regarding the approach to the problem, the research was considered as quantitative, qualitative or quali-quantitative. It can be seen that the qualitative research of this study involved obtaining data from the interviewees carried out. These data were obtained through direct contact with the researcher in the research interview situation. Quantitative research only makes sense when there is a very well-defined problem and there is information and theory regarding the object of knowledge, understood here as the focus of the research and/or what you want to study. To clarify further, quantitative research can only be carried out when the qualities are known and you have control over what you are researching. (SILVA & SIMON, 2005).

As for technical procedures, it is a bibliographical research and case study. Bibliographical research is carried out by surveying theoretical references that have already been analyzed and published through written and electronic means, such as books, scientific articles, web pages and websites, with the objective of collecting information or prior knowledge about the problem. from which the answer is sought. (FONSECA, 2002, p. 32). And it is a case study because it investigates a phenomenon within a real-life context. In the view of Goode and Hatt (1979), they define the case study as a method of looking at social reality. "It is not a specific technique; it is a means of organizing social data while preserving the unitary character of the social object studied".

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the company's initial implementation, 12 fuel tanks made of carbon steel were installed; this tanking area is responsible for storing petroleum derivatives and biofuels. The fuels that are stored in the company's tank park come from national and international refineries, with the capacity of each oil tanker being 100,000 tons. Figure 1 below represents the company's tank park and river terminal.

Figure 1 – Tanking and river terminal

Source: Port Information (2016)

The company has several sectors that are well distributed and carry out multidisciplinary tasks, however, the operating sector is directly linked to the loading and unloading transfer operation of ships, ferries and tank trucks. The operation is responsible for planning operations, unloading and loading ships and ferries, manual sampling in land tanks and pipelines, level measurement and drainage of tanks, temperature reading in tanks, sample control, connection and disconnection of hoses on ships and ferries, operation of the water and oil separator, use of the support boat when docking and undocking ships and ferries, supplying tugboats, supplying on the road platform and unloading tank truck operations. Below are the procedures that must be carried out for loading and unloading fuels and derivatives.

- i. Operations planning: an analysis of the physical stock is carried out in order to assess the availability of available unloading space and the pumpable volume of cargo. Next, an operations plan is prepared by activity and the employees who will operate in each work shift are sized and, finally, assessments are carried out regarding the operational conditions and verification of the performances of the cataloged vessels.
- ii. Ship and ferry unloading operation: establishes the procedures that must be carried out for unloading both, marking registration in the “MEGA fuels”

movement system. Furthermore, it carries out the unloading of ships and ferries, checking the operation modality based on their planning, as well as authorizing and monitoring dockings based on the operation planning and systematic discussion on board by through meetings to define operational criteria. After surveying the lines, valves and pumps of the tanks that are used in the operation, it is necessary to check the Terminal inspection, identifying whether there was any anomaly in the system and determining the standardization of pumping interruptions to ensure that there are no variations in the system. tank levels.

- iii. Loading of ships and ferries: it is necessary to comply with the loading procedures for ships and ferries, checking the mode of operation through operational planning, authorizing and monitoring the docking of the vessel at the Terminal, and meeting on board the Terminal to share information on all operational aspects. In addition, the lines, valves and pumps used in the operation are aligned, and then the Terminal is inspected for periodic rounds every half hour, checking whether the circuits are perfect and leak-free and determining a percentage parameter for the interruption of pumping in the control room.
- iv. Reading in tanks: the materials and equipment that must be used for this procedure are determined and the tanks that must be taken at temperature are defined in accordance with the Terminal's activity schedule.
- v. Connecting and disconnecting hoses on ships and ferries: defines the criteria for connecting and disconnecting hoses on ferries and ships, informing the times for performing the services, in addition to determining which lines are for connection or disconnection, as well as preparing for connection and disconnection, lifting the hoses and connecting, evaluating the connections so that the operation can be recorded.
- vi. Use of the support boat when docking and undocking ships and ferries: the Terminal's port support boat must be made available, inspect the support boat periodically and ensure that all safety, communication and functioning items are in place, carrying out a daily schedule communication in the control room and support the docking and undocking of ships and ferries.
- vii. Tank truck unloading operation: the tank truck unloading procedure is followed, registering the vehicle in the MEGA system, defining the tank, line and valve, as well as carrying out Terminal checks before unloading the truck, communicating the arrival of the tanker truck and authorizing unloading, inspecting and analyzing

the product, issuing documentation releasing the operational area. Figure 2 below shows the terminal's lines and tanks.

Figure 2 – Tanking lines and park

Source: Port Information (2016)

Currently, the company has 16 tanks for storing fuels such as Anhydrous Ethanol, Diesel AS10, Marine Diesel, Biodiesel, Gasoline A and Diesel AS500 and another 2 tanks for storing contaminated waste that is removed from the 16 tanks.

Table 1 below shows the number of tanks that the company currently has, the storage capacity of each tank in cubic meters (m³), maximum and minimum operating capacity in m³, the elevation of each tank in meters and the elevation of the top of the tank in meters (m).

Table 1 – Tank characteristics

Tank	Product	Average Int. Diameter (m)	Useful Height (m)	Tabled Capacity (m³)
TQ-01	Class I, II	28,463	16.83	10,738.34
TQ-02	Class I, II	19,967	16.72	5,240.20
TQ-03	Class I, II	19,998	16.71	5,264.08
TQ-04	Class I, II	19.99	16.77	5,278.76
TQ-05	Class I, II	19,997	16.83	5,310.10
TQ-06	Class I, II	19,965	16.76	5,268.82
TQ-07	Class I, II	19,987	16.72	5,263.99
TQ-08	Class I, II	19,989	16.79	5,289.10
TQ-09	Class I, II	14.5	14.31	2,370.68
TQ-10	Class III	14,502	14.32	2,371.22
TQ-11	Class I, II	19,982	16.64	5,234.74
TQ-12	Class I, II	19,986	16.73	5,265.08
TQ-13	Contaminated	4,994	5.98	117.42
TQ-14	Contaminated	3,495	4.87	46,917
TQ-15	Class I, II, III	28,616	17.02	11,019.34
TQ-16	Class I, II, III	28,616	15.98	10,350.28
TQ-17	Class I, II, III	28,616	17.02	11,031.26
TQ-18	Class I, II, III	28,616	17.02	11,018.11

Source: The authors (2022)

Regarding the load lines, it is considered that the lines have a flow rate of approximately 1250 m³/h, in which the load *manifolds are connected to ducts with a diameter of 14" (fourteen inches) and provide load for a module of storage of the 16 tanks, with the furthest tank being 700 m from the river terminal.* Figure 3 below shows the terminal's load lines.

Figure 3 – Terminal Load Lines

Source: The authors (2022)

3.1. Private use terminal

Table 2 below represents the reference record for standardized services, taking into account the private use of the company's terminal. This table concerns the type of service that the company offers to its customers.

Table 2 – Reference record

REFERENCE RATES		
01	Dedicated tank	Not available
02	Minimum storage period	15 days
03	Docking and undocking service (per ship)	R\$ 16,000.00
04	Pier usage fee – first 24 hours	R\$ 14,985.00
05	Pier usage fee – surplus per 24 hours (per 4 hours)	R\$ 4,246.25
06	Naval and river reception, storage and river shipping	R\$ 120.00 /m ³
07	Road expedition	R\$ 80.00 /m ³
08	Other product movements	R\$ 120.00 /m ³
TAXES (ON THE VALUE OF THE SERVICE)		
09	ISS	5%
10	PIS	1.65%
11	COFINS	7.6%
12	FUNDAF (by daily request for the presence of customs inspection)	R\$ 582.00
13	Foremanship fee per BL	R\$ 1,000.00

Source: The authors (2022)

Table 3 is a practical guide on how fuel should be loaded by road. It can be seen that for loading, it is necessary to make use of island A with four loading arms and through them, hydrated Ethanol can pass; Diesel Oil and Gasoline C.

Table 3 – Road loading platform

Identification	Number of Loading Arms	Products
Island “A”	4	BC-01– Hydrated ethanol
		BC-02 – Diesel oil
		BC-03 – Gasoline C

Source: The authors (2022)

Table 4 – Interconnection pipelines with the floating dock

Diameter (in)	Product	Length (m)	Origin	Destiny
12” - BD	Biodiesel	580	Tank Basin	Ship Unloading
14” - GA-A	Gasoline–A	580	Tank Basin	Ship Unloading
14” - AH	Hydrous ethanol	580	Tank Basin	Ship Unloading
14” - AA	Anhydrous Ethanol	580	Tank Basin	Ship Unloading
14” - DS-1	Diesel	506	Tank Basin	Ship Unloading
14” - DS-2	Diesel	506	Tank Basin	Ship Unloading
14” - DS-3	Diesel	506	Tank Basin	Ship Unloading

Source: The authors (2022)

Table 5 – Pipelines for Ferry Loading

Diameter (inch)	Product	Length (m)	Origin	Destiny
8” - AH	Hydrous ethanol	250	Bomb Transfer Area	Ferry Loading
8” - AA	Anhydrous Ethanol	250	Bomb Transfer Area	Ferry Loading
12” - DS-1	Diesel	500	Bomb Transfer Area	Ferry Loading
12” - DS-2	Diesel	500	Bomb Transfer Area	Ferry Loading
12” - DS-3	Diesel	500	Bomb Transfer Area	Ferry Loading
12” - GA-A	Gasoline–A	500	Bomb Transfer Area	Ferry Loading
8” - BD	Biodiesel	250	Bomb Transfer Area	Ferry Loading
8” - BD	Contaminated	504	Unloading Ferries and Ships	Tank 13

Source: The authors (2022)

3.2. Product movement

The following tables represent the movement of products such as Marine Diesel, Diesel A S500, Diesel A S10, Biodiesel, Gasoline A and Anhydrous Ethanol, between January and May 2022, through river and road modes.

In the month of January 2022, the previous balance was 588325 liters of Marine Diesel, a further 1262678 liters were stored via river mode and 1633816 liters were distributed, there was no loading or unloading via road mode, computing a current balance of 217187 liters of Diesel Maritime. The previous balance of AS500 Diesel was 10107760 liters, a further 110588286

liters were stored via river mode and 8982184 liters were distributed. There was no entry of Diesel AS500 by road, but 26810 liters were distributed, accounting for a current balance of 31187052 liters of Diesel AS500. The previous balance of Diesel AS10 was 7738892 liters, a further 76788649 liters were stored via river mode and 69909048 liters were distributed. There was no entry or exit of Diesel AS10 via road, accounting for a current balance of 14618493 liters of Diesel AS10.

The previous balance of Biodiesel was 635,418 liters, a further 970,600 liters were stored via river transport and 616,431 liters were distributed. There was no entry of Biodiesel via road transport, but 482,799 liters were distributed, accounting for a current balance of 506,788 liters of Biodiesel. The previous balance of Gasoline A was 4965989 liters, a further 54947184 liters were stored via river mode and 53232782 liters were distributed. There was no product loading via road mode, but 194403 liters were discharged, accounting for a current balance of 6485988 liters of Gasoline A. The previous balance of Anhydrous Ethanol was 2160785 liters, a further 1239160 liters were stored via river mode and 1873268 liters were distributed, via road mode there was no product loading, but 114679 liters were discharged, accounting for a balance current 1411998 liters of Anhydrous Ethanol.

Graph 1 – Product movements in January 2022

Source: The authors (2022)

In the month of February 2022, the previous balance was 217,187 liters of Marine Diesel, a further 3,474,814 liters were stored via river transport and there was no product distribution. In the road mode, there was no loading of Marine Diesel, but there was an unloading of 3046386 liters, computing a current balance of 645615 liters of Marine Diesel. The previous balance of Diesel AS500 was 31187052 liters, a further 95498483 liters were stored via river transport and 100137222 liters were distributed. There was no entry of Diesel AS500 by road, but 49500

liters were distributed, accounting for a current balance of 26498813 liters of Diesel AS500. The previous balance of AS10 Diesel was 14618493 liters, a further 92311511 liters were stored via river mode and 86767023 liters were distributed.

There was no entry of Diesel AS10 by road, but 4500 liters were distributed, accounting for a current balance of 20158481 liters of Diesel AS10. The previous balance of Biodiesel was 635,418 liters, a further 970,600 liters were stored via river transport and 616,431 liters were distributed. There was no entry of Biodiesel via road transport, but 482,799 liters were distributed, accounting for a current balance of 506,788 liters of Biodiesel. The previous balance of Gasoline A was 6485988 liters, a further 36481725 liters were stored via the river modal and distributed 37831166 liters, via the road modal there was no product loading, but 208050 liters were discharged, accounting for a current balance of 4928497 liters of Gasoline A. The previous balance of Anhydrous Ethanol was 1411998 liters, an additional 100000 liters were stored via river mode and 877960 liters were distributed. There was no product loading via road mode, but 76950 liters were discharged, accounting for a current balance of 557088 liters of Anhydrous Ethanol.

Graph 2 – Product movements in February 2022

Source: The authors (2022)

In the month of March 2022, the previous balance was 645615 liters of Marine Diesel, a further 3453118 liters were stored via river transport and 3394419 liters were distributed. In the road mode, there was no loading of Marine Diesel, but there was an unloading of 18,862 liters, resulting in a current balance of 685,452 liters of Marine Diesel. The previous balance of Diesel AS500 was 26498813 liters, a further 78791556 liters were stored via river transport and 97529710 liters were distributed. There was no entry of Diesel AS500 by road, but 25,931 liters were distributed, accounting for a current balance of 7734,728 liters of Diesel AS500. The

previous balance of AS10 Diesel was 20158481 liters, a further 53446317 liters were stored via river mode and 71189949 liters were distributed. There was no entry or exit of Diesel AS10 via road, accounting for a current balance of 2414849 liters of Diesel AS10.

The previous balance of Biodiesel was 469,599 liters, a further 390,110 liters were stored via river transport and 130,652 liters were distributed. There was no entry of Biodiesel by road, but 360,589 liters were distributed, accounting for a current balance of 368,468 liters of Biodiesel. The previous balance of Gasoline A was 4928497 liters, a further 55880023 liters were stored via river mode and distributed 53250434 liters. There was no loading or unloading of product via road mode, accounting for a current balance of 7558086 liters of Gasoline A. The balance previous amount of Anhydrous Ethanol was 557,088 liters, there was no loading or unloading of product for both the river and road modes, accounting for a current balance of 557,088 liters of Anhydrous Ethanol.

Graph 3 – Product movements in March 2022

Source: The authors (2022)

In the month of April 2022, the previous balance was 685,452 liters of Marine Diesel, an additional 3,139,165 liters were stored via river transport and 1,749,298 liters were distributed. In the road mode, there was no loading and unloading of Marine Diesel, resulting in a current balance of 2075319 liters of Marine Diesel. The previous balance of AS500 Diesel was 7734728 liters, a further 56817792 liters were stored via river mode and 63136075 liters were distributed. There was no entry of Diesel AS500 by road, but 23300 liters were distributed, accounting for a current balance of 1391345 liters of Diesel AS500. The previous balance of AS10 Diesel was 2414849 liters, a further 88759073 liters were stored via river mode and 89804299 liters were distributed. There was no entry or exit of Diesel AS10 via road, accounting for a current balance of 1369623 liters of Diesel AS10.

The previous balance of Biodiesel was 368,468 liters, there was no storage of product via river mode, but 130,671 liters were distributed. There was no entry of Biodiesel via road transport, but 2584 liters were distributed, accounting for a current balance of 235213 liters of Biodiesel. The previous balance of Gasoline A was 7558086 liters, a further 59994303 liters were stored via river mode and distributed 57049639 liters. There was no loading or unloading of product via road mode, accounting for a current balance of 10502750 liters of Gasoline A. The balance of Anhydrous Ethanol was 557,088 liters, there was no loading or unloading of product by river mode, there was also no loading by road mode, but there was a product discharge of 297,447 liters, accounting for a current balance of 259,641 liters of Anhydrous Ethanol.

Graph 4 – Product movements in April 2022

Source: The authors (2022)

In the month of May 2022, the previous balance was 2075319 liters of Marine Diesel, a further 2347467 liters were stored via river mode and 3028015 liters distributed. In the road mode, there was no load of Marine Diesel, but 29,794 liters were distributed, accounting for a current balance of 1364,997 liters of Marine Diesel. The previous balance of Diesel AS500 was 1393145 liters, a further 92183277 liters were stored via river transport and 87558485 liters were distributed. There was no entry of Diesel AS500 by road, but 35760 liters were distributed, accounting for a current balance of 5982177 liters of Diesel AS500. The previous balance of AS10 Diesel was 1369623 liters, a further 118240649 liters were stored via river mode and 95894785 liters were distributed. There was no entry or exit of Diesel AS10 via road, accounting for a current balance of 23715487 liters of Diesel AS10. The previous balance of Biodiesel was 235,213 liters, 605,646 liters were loaded via river transport and 36,795 liters were distributed. There was no product storage via road transport, but 3,974 liters were distributed, accounting for a current balance of 800,090 liters of Biodiesel.

Graph 5 – Product movements in May 2022

Source: The authors (2022)

The previous balance of Gasoline A was 10502750 liters, a further 47766613 liters were stored via river mode and distributed 49001091 liters. There was no loading or unloading of product via road mode, accounting for a current balance of 9268272 liters of Gasoline A. The balance of Anhydrous Ethanol was 259,641 liters, there was no product loading via river mode, but 32,159 liters were distributed. By road, there was no product loading, but 227,482 liters were unloaded, accounting for a current balance of 0 liters of Anhydrous Ethanol.

4. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The research aimed to analyze how the process of storing fuels derived from liquid petroleum and biofuels is carried out in the tank park of the company River Terminals in Brazil – RTB and their distribution, identifying the modal types used through means of transport, such as ferry, ship and truck, with the maritime sector being the ferry and the ship and the road transport being the truck. Furthermore, determine the quantity of products such as Marine Diesel, Diesel A S500, Diesel A S10, Biodiesel, Gasoline A and Anhydrous Ethanol, between January and May 2022.

Data were collected in two phases, secondary and primary. Secondary data were tabulated through consultations on websites, social networks and scientific articles published by the company analyzed in annals and academic events, for the theoretical basis of the research. As for primary data, a technical visit was carried out to identify how the fuel loading and unloading process works between the modes used by the organization and an interview with employees in the operational sector who work directly in the storage and distribution of products.

The procedures for loading and unloading products at the Terminal consist of operation planning. This planning is essential in preparing the activities that must be carried out. For the loading and unloading of ships and ferries, movement records must be signed in Mega Fuel and

verifying the type of operation. Next, the lines, valves and pumps of the tanks used in the operation are surveyed, carrying out inspections of the Terminal. To read the temperature in tanks, the materials that must be used are checked and the tanks that must be taken at temperature are defined in accordance with the Terminal's activity schedule. When connecting and disconnecting on ships and ferries, after defining the criteria for connecting and disconnecting hoses on ferries and ships, the hoses must be lifted and connected. The tank truck unloading operation defines the tank, line and valve, as well as carrying out Terminal checks before unloading the truck, communicating the arrival of the tank truck and authorizing the unloading, inspecting and analyzing the product, issuing release documentation from the operational area.

In view of the facts mentioned, it can be seen that during the research, the information acquired about loading and unloading procedures, modes of transport and quantity of product movement were enlightening in understanding the internal functioning of the company. In addition to understanding the company's contribution in terms of supply to the states of Amazonas, Acre, Rondônia, Pará and Mato Grosso, through its ease in the operational process and the relevance of the study to the area of Production Engineering, with an emphasis on logistics carriage.

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